

EFFECTIVENESS OF PRINCIPALS EXEMPLARY LEADERSHIP PRACTICED ON SCHOOL ACHIEVEMENTS: STAKEHOLDERS' PERCEPTIONS

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Abstract:

The study examines the effectiveness of principals' exemplary leadership practiced on school achievements as perceived by stakeholders. The respondents were 193 stakeholders comprised Senior Assistants, Afternoon session School Supervisors, Officers of District Education Office, teachers, and, representatives of Parent Teacher Association. The study adapted the Leadership Practices Inventory (LPI) model developed by Kouzes and Posner (2001, 2004). The data collected from the survey were analysed using a statistical software package, Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 23.0. The results showed that the component 'Enable Others to Act' was the most effective practiced with the highest mean score of 4.12 and standard deviation 0.700. The second highest was 'Challenge the Process' with mean 4.01 and standard deviation 0.764. The third highest was 'Encourages the Heart' with mean 4.00 and standard deviation 0.771. It was followed by 'Inspired a Shared Vision' with mean 3.97 and standard deviation 0.739. On the other hand, the stakeholders have identified the lowest score was the component 'Model of the Way' with mean 3.77 and standard deviation 0.768. It is hoped that this study would effectively benefit leaders and educators in schools towards realization of the Malaysian Education Development Plan 2013-2025.

Keywords: principals, exemplary leadership effectiveness, school achievements

1. Introduction

The Ministry has continuously outlined many programs and courses to train the educational leaders so that they would contribute to the high achievement of schools

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through collaboration with many institutions local and abroad. These principals are fully trusted and given high responsibility after attending such programmes or training to meet the needs of each school, Ministry of Education and of course to Malaysia for its continuous development. It is essential to examine whether the Exemplary Leadership practices are carried out while performing their duties and how effective is the Exemplary Leadership practices contribute to the school achievement. The Exemplary Leadership practices that they perform shall help them to uplifting their level of school ranking in equivalent to the government's national agenda for education.

2. Literature Review: Exemplary Leadership

Browning (2007) stated that leadership is an attribution which is dependent on many aspects of behavior which will be required to change in concert with the changing situation. Cowie & Crawford (2007) stated that a good leader depends on quality, values and resources available to deal with the current environment. Brauckmann & Pashiardis (2011) agreed that Leadership is the key factor to the success of any schools. Duignan, (2007) observed that management practices are the leadership activities concentrated and concerned on life of the organization. Leaders dealt with organizational members and ensure that organizational tasks are accomplished.

Kouzes and Posner (2007) affirmed that the leadership is a skill and ability that can be enhanced and improved upon through the desire to become a better leader. Kouzes and Posner (2003) emphasized the Leadership Practices Inventory (LPI) that focuses on the behavioral factors contributed to the Leadership effective practices. Kouzes and Posner (2002) earlier had created a Model of Exemplary Leadership serving as a desirable technique and represent the best kind of its model as it removes the organizational barriers. It usually has its solution to solve problem that arises with certain practices. The five dimensions of Exemplary Leadership are as follows:

a. Modeling the way

Leaders who succeeded within this leadership practice established principles for themselves and demonstrated a commitment to their values on a daily basis. These leaders spent time with their followers often working next to them or asking questions to encourage followers to determine their own values (Kouzes & Posner, 2002). *"Modeling the way is essentially about earning the right and the respect to lead through direct individual involvement and action. People first follow the person, then the plan"* (Kouzes & Posner, 2002).

The most common view of leadership is to influence as role models for their followers, inspirational motivation which involves motivating and inspiring followers by providing meaning and challenge to their work, intellectual stimulation which involves stimulating followers' efforts to be innovative and creative, individualized consideration which involves paying special attention to each individual's needs for achievement and growth (Bass and Avolio, 1994).

b. Inspiring a shared vision

Leaders who displayed behaviors within this leadership practice have a desire to create something new. They had a picture in their mind, and they worked to make that picture a reality. These leaders knew the dreams, values, hopes and aspirations of their followers. They spoke the same language as their followers and used that language to enlist the followers to achieve the same vision (Kouzes & Posner, 2002).

Mulford & Sillins (2011), a principal who can bring harmony in values and beliefs underlying the school's goal and objectives will be most likely to influence teacher's work and student achievement. Orphanos & Orr (2011) affirmed that an excellent of practices which is embedded in the principal personality, shall promote a school should have a clear mission or set of a goals.

c. Challenging the process

This practice was exhibited by leaders who were willing to step into the unknown. These leaders searched for opportunities to innovate and improve. "Innovation comes from listening than telling" (Kouzes & Posner, 2002). The leaders' primary contribution was to recognize and support new ideas in addition to getting new products and systems adopted. *"Leaders also pay attention to the capacity of their constituents to take control of challenging situations and become fully committed to change"* (Kouzes & Posner, 2002).

The school needs a leader who has the intellectual stimulation which means challenging teachers to professionalize themselves in such a manner that the organization is learning a whole (Leithwood, 1996)

d. Enabling others to act

This practice was demonstrated by leaders who fostered collaboration and built trust among their followers so good work was completed. These leaders did not keep power to themselves; they "work to make people feel strong, capable, and committed" (Kouzes & Posner, 2002). When followers felt trusted and were given discretion to make decision, they worked hard and surpassed their own expectations (Kouzes & Posner, 2002).

Qing, Day & Ko (2010) believes that the practices cover a wide area that is robust with underlying dimensions of leadership that can lead school and classroom strategies and actions that school principals and staff have adopted to raise pupil attainment which later will turn into predicted improvement in schools' academic performance.

e. Encourage the hearts

This practice was exhibited by leaders who recognized the contributions made by other individuals (Kouzes & Posner, 2002). Leaders used celebrations and rituals to allow others to recognize the benefits of aligning behavior with values. In addition, leaders created strong collective identity that carried a group through tough times (Kouzes & Posner, 2002).

The individual consideration is factor to concern and respect for the personal feelings and needs of teacher. Leadership fosters the basic needs of followers, emphasizes the transaction or exchange between leaders and their followers, and is characterized by management by exception and contingent reward. The leader also tells the staff what to do to be rewarded for their efforts (Leithwood, 1994).

Previous researches on effective school have agreed that principals with strong leadership skills and a willingness to participate actively in activities tend to create better schools (Zigarelli, 1996, Duignan, 2007, and Hallinger & Heck, 2010). Sammons, Qing, Day & Ko (2010) believes that the practices cover a wide area that is robust with underlying dimensions of leadership that can lead school and classroom strategies and actions that school principals and staff have adopted to raise pupil attainment which later will turn into predicted improvement in schools' academic performance.

The principals' leadership and engagement had demonstrated commitment, sensitivity, and focuses on continuous improvement and openness to information and diverse views, strongly impacts student performance (Mwangi, 2009). According to Taylor and William (2001), the principal should be responsible to examining the strategies as alternative use of time and they are accountable to develop strategies for working as a team rather than using fear tactics or raising stress level among teachers and administrators.

According to Malaysian educative leadership in their interim research findings (Mohamad Johdi 2010, Hairudin (2012), and, Nazifah 2013), leaders are to make sure that schools operate smoothly, that leaders are firm in implementing decisions and that they distribute workloads fairly. Bush (2010) and Corcoran (2012) observed other management services values include the leaders' capacities to maximize the use of limited resources, to provide problem-solving processes, and to promote the growth of knowledge about teaching and evaluation services. Hairuddin (2010) affirmed that they help a school community to monitor outcomes, compare outcomes and achieve objectives. They also develop new objectives, revise goals and strategies.

Recent studies on principal leadership focused on a school turnaround which accumulates the specific behavior or personality traits in improving school leadership practices (Neil, 2012). It was supported by productive leadership traits and behaviors provide insight to education leaders in interested in helping their school achievement (Davies & Davies, 2010, and, Sternke, 2011). Even though traits and behavior provides fact for current studies, values, beliefs and principle also indicated as supported factors that encourage principal engagement in leadership sustainability (Gurr, Drysdale, Ylimaki & Jacobson, 2011). Professional development can be prepared with relevant leadership knowledge, skills and attitude in order to face the 21st century challenges especially related to multicultural school environment.

Kouzes & Posner (2002) believe that the exemplary leadership can perhaps bring out changes and creates new dimension that have some influencing measurement on the followers. It also influences the followers in terms of trust, admiration, loyalty and respect towards leaders. Thus, the leader provides followers with an inspiring mission and vision, motivates followers through their hearts, intend to apply intellectual

through stimulation and individual consideration. It is about leadership practice on model the way, inspire a shared vision, challenge the process, enable others to act and encourage the heart (Kouzes & Posner, 2007).

Hence, the researcher would like to conduct this study that will discover the educational leader's ability to guide the followers to the common practices through the model of Exemplary Leadership developed by Kouzes and Posner (2002).

3. Aim of the Study and Research Questions

The purpose of this study is to examine the effective practiced of Exemplary Leadership by principals on school achievements at selected secondary schools in the State of Selangor, Malaysia. This research will focus on the perception of stakeholders comprised the senior assistants, teachers, Parent Teacher Association representatives and district education officer towards the principals' exemplary leadership practices. It is to seek and revise some of the major gaps in the present literature on Exemplary Leadership of principals in Malaysia as a general context. More specifically, the study aims to seek answers to the following research questions:

1. What are the stakeholders' perceptions on effectiveness of Principals' Model the Way practiced on school achievements?
2. What are the stakeholders' perceptions on effectiveness of Principals' Inspired a shared vision practiced on school achievements?
3. What are the stakeholders' perceptions on effectiveness of Principals' Challenge the process practiced on school achievements?
4. What are the stakeholders' perceptions on effectiveness of Principals' Enable others to act practiced on school achievements?
5. What are the stakeholders' perceptions on effectiveness of Principals' Encourage the heart practiced on school achievements?

4. Methodology of Study

This study used the Leadership Practices Inventory (LPI) developed by Kouzes and Posner (2004) emphasizing a multi-item scale on Exemplary leadership style. The self-administered survey used purposive sampling where the list was taken from the rank of 60 high achievement schools based on Lower Secondary Assessment achievement from the year 2014 until 2017. The study involved 193 stakeholders of secondary schools in Selangor, comprised the Senior Assistants (Academic), Senior Assistants (Curriculum), Afternoon session school supervisors, Officers of District Education Office (*Pejabat Pelajaran Daerah -PPD*), teachers, and, representatives of Parent Teacher Association (PTA-PIBG).

The questionnaire required respondents to answer by using numerical scores with the 5-point Likert scale, i.e. 1- Not effective, 2- Rarely effective, 3- Fairly effective, 4- Effective, and, 5- Very effective. The data collected from the survey were analysed using a statistical software package, Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version

23.0. The analysis will find the frequencies and percentages of demographic variables in order to understand the demographic characteristics of the sample. The findings of the study were presented in the following sections.

5. Results of the Study

Tables 1 to 5 presented the Effectiveness of Exemplary Leadership Practices of Principals on School Achievements in Malaysia as perceived by Stakeholders.

Research Question 1: The Stakeholders' Perceptions on Effectiveness of Model the Way Practiced on School Achievements by Principals of Secondary Schools, Malaysia.

The stakeholders' perceptions on effectiveness of Model the Way practiced by principals on school achievements in Malaysia is presented on Table 1 below.

Table 1: Effectiveness of Model the Way on School Achievements as practiced by Principals of Secondary Schools, Malaysia: Stakeholders' Perceptions (n=193)

No	Items	Score, Frequency & Percentage (%)					Mean	SD
		1	2	3	4	5		
1	He seeks out challenging opportunities that test his own skills and abilities	2 (1)	0	62 (32.1)	113 (58.6)	16 (8.3)	3.73	0.653
2	He challenges people to try out new and innovative approaches to our work	2 (1)	12 (6.2)	61 (31.7)	95 (49.2)	23 (11.9)	3.65	0.81
3	He searches outside the formal boundaries of my organization for innovative ways to improve what we do	2 (1)	7 (3.6)	47 (24.4)	103 (53.4)	34 (17.6)	3.83	0.795
4	He asks "What can we learn?" when things do not go as expected	4 (2.1)	9 (4.7)	59 (30.6)	93 (48.2)	28 (14.4)	3.68	0.853
5	He experiments and takes risks even when there is a chance of failure	2 (1)	2 (1)	48 (24.9)	109 (56.5)	32 (16.6)	3.87	0.731
6	He takes the initiative to overcome obstacles even when outcomes are uncertain	3 (1.6)	1 (0.5)	50 (25.9)	104 (53.9)	35 (18.1)	3.87	0.765
Sub-total (Average)							3.77	0.768

Score: 1= Not effective, 2=Rarely effective, 3=Fairly effective, 4=Effective, 5=Very effective

Table 1 illustrated "Model of the way" mainly from the stakeholders' perception on effectiveness of Exemplary leadership. It was found that there were two statements achieved the same score. The first statement was "He experiments and takes risks even when there is a chance of failure", the majority with 109 respondents responded that it was "Effective" with 56.5% of the result obtained. Another 48 respondents responded to "Fairly Effective" with 24.9% and 32 respondents responded to "Very Effective" by 16.6% of the result. But, 2 respondents responded to "Rarely Effective" and "Not Effective" which contributed 1% each to the result obtained. Therefore, the mean score for the above statement was 3.87 with a standard deviation of 0.731.

The second statement was "He takes the initiative to overcome obstacles even when outcomes are uncertain", with a majority of 53.9% indicated "Effective" with 104

respondents agreed to the statement and 50 respondents responded 25.9% to the statement of "Fairly Effective". A minority of respondent 18.1% indicated "Very Effective" with 35 respondents agreed to it. However, 3 respondents with 1.6% indicated "Not Effective" and 1 respondent with 0.5% agreed to "Rarely Effective" on the statement above. As a result, the mean score for the above statement was 3.87 with a standard deviation of 0.765.

In contrast, the lowest score for the above statement "He challenges people to try out new and innovative approaches to our work" indicated that 95 respondents with 49.2% agreed to "Effective" and 61 respondents with 31.7% agreed to "Fairly Effective". However, only 23 respondents agreed to "Very Effective" with 11.9% and 12 respondents responded to "Rarely Effective" with 6.2%. Nevertheless, 2 respondents with 1% agreed to "Not Effective". Therefore, the mean score for the above statement was 3.65 with a standard deviation of 0.810.

Research Question 2: The Stakeholders' Perceptions on Effectiveness of Inspired a Shared Vision Practiced on School Achievements by Principals of Secondary Schools, Malaysia.

The stakeholders' perceptions on effectiveness of Inspired a Shared Vision practiced by principals on school achievements in Malaysia is presented on Table 2 below.

Table 2: Effectiveness of Inspired a Shared Vision on School Achievements as practiced by Principals of Secondary Schools, Malaysia: Stakeholders' Perceptions (n=193)

No	Items	Score, Frequency & Percentage (%)					Mean	SD
		1	2	3	4	5		
1	He talks about future trends that will influence how our work gets done	2 (1)	3 (1.6)	49 (25.4)	107 (55.4)	32 (16.6)	3.85	0.745
2	He describes a compelling image of what our future could be like	2 (1)	5 (2.6)	37 (19.2)	106 (54.9)	43 (22.3)	3.95	0.782
3	He appeals to others to share an exciting dream of the future	5 (2.6)	6 (3.1)	61 (31.6)	96 (49.7)	25 (13)	3.67	0.837
4	He shows others how their long-term interests can be realized by enlisting in a common vision	1 (0.5)	5 (2.6)	41 (21.2)	107 (55.4)	39 (20.3)	3.92	0.749
5	He is contagiously enthusiastic and positive about future possibilities	1 (0.5)	0	22 (11.4)	106 (54.9)	64 (33.2)	4.2	0.674
6	He speaks with genuine conviction about the higher meaning and purpose of work	0	1 (0.5)	21 (10.9)	106 (54.9)	65 (33.7)	4.22	0.649
	Sub-total (Average)						3.97	0.739

Note: SD = Standard Deviation, *f* = Frequency, (number) = (%)

Score: 1=Not effective, 2=Rarely effective, 3=Fairly effective, 4=Effective, 5=Very effective.

Table 2 illustrated that the highest score statement for "Inspired a shared vision" was "He is contagiously enthusiastic and positive about future possibilities". In response to the statement, about 106 respondents agreed to "Effective" that contributed 54.9% to the result. Other responses to this statement included 64 respondents agreed to "Very

Effective” that contributed 33.2% and 22 respondents agreed to “Fairly Effective” that contributed 11.4%. However, 1 respondent agreed to “Not Effective” with 0.5% contribution to the result. Therefore, the mean score for the above statement was 4.2 with a standard deviation of 0.6740.

In contrast, the lowest for the above mean was “He appeals others to share an exciting dream of the future”. The results of this statement showed that 96 respondents agreed to “Effective” with 49.7% contributions to the result obtained. While 61 respondents agreed to “Fairly Effective” with only 31.6% and 25 respondents agreed to “Very Effective” with 13%. Anyhow, 6 respondents agreed to “Rarely Effective” with 3.1% and 5 respondents agreed to “Not Effective” which consisted of 2.6% contribution to the result. Therefore, the mean score for the above statement was 3.67 with a standard deviation of 0.837.

Research Question 3: The Stakeholders’ Perceptions on Effectiveness of Challenge the Process Practiced on School Achievements by Principals of Secondary Schools, Malaysia.

The stakeholders’ perceptions on effectiveness of Challenge the Process practiced by principals on school achievements in Malaysia is presented on Table 3 below.

Table 3: Effectiveness of Challenge the Process on School Achievements as practiced by Principals of Secondary Schools, Malaysia: Stakeholders’ Perceptions (n=193)

No	Items	Score, Frequency & Percentage (%)					Mean	SD
		1	2	3	4	5		
1	He develops cooperative relationships among the people I work with	1 (0.5)	0	28 (14.5)	96 (49.7)	68 (35.3)	4.19	0.714
2	He actively listens to diverse points of view	1 (0.5)	3 (1.6)	41 (21.2)	98 (50.8)	50 (25.9)	4	0.764
3	He treats others with dignity and respect	0	1 (0.5)	21 (10.9)	84 (43.5)	87 (45.1)	4.33	0.688
4	He supports the decisions that people make on their own	6 (3.1)	17 (8.8)	72 (37.3)	75 (38.9)	23 (11.9)	3.48	0.925
5	He gives people a great deal of freedom and choice in deciding how to do their work	1 (0.5)	1 (0.5)	42 (21.8)	98 (50.8)	51 (26.4)	4.02	0.743
6	He ensures that people grow in their job by learning new skills and developing themselves	2 (1)	3 (1.6)	29 (15)	110 (57)	49 (25.4)	4.04	0.749
Sub-total (Average)							4.01	0.764

Note: SD = Standard Deviation, f = Frequency, (number) = (%)

Score: 1=Not effective, 2=Rarely effective, 3=Fairly effective, 4=Effective, 5=Very effective

Table 3 presented that the highest score statement for “Challenge the process” was “He treats others with dignity and respect” that managed to gain 87 respondents to agree with “Very Effective” that contributed 45.1% and 84 respondents preferred “Effective” with 43.5% of the result. Only 21 respondents find the statement “Fairly Effective” with 10.9%. Yet, 1 respondent finds it “Rarely Effective” with 0.5% contributions to the result

obtained. Therefore, the mean score for the above statement was 4.33 with a standard deviation of 0.688.

In contrast, the lowest for the above mean was “He supports the decisions that people make on their own”. It was interesting to note that in this statement, 75 respondents chose “Effective” which contributed 38.9% of the results and 72 respondents responded to “Fairly Effective” with 37.3%. In addition, only 23 respondents preferred “Very Effective” that contributed only 11.9% and 17 respondents responded to “Rarely Effective” with 8.8%. However, 6 respondents chose “Not Effective” that contributed only 3.1%. Therefore, the mean score for the above statement was 3.48 with a standard deviation of 0.925.

Research Question 4: The Stakeholders’ Perceptions on Effectiveness of Enable Others to Act Practiced on School Achievements by Principals of Secondary Schools, Malaysia.

The stakeholders’ perceptions on effectiveness of ‘Enable Others to Act’ practiced by principals on school achievements in Malaysia is presented on Table 4 below.

Table 4: Effectiveness of Enable Others to Act on School Achievements as practiced by Principals of Secondary Schools, Malaysia: Stakeholders’ Perceptions (n=193)

No	Items	Score, Frequency & Percentage (%)					Mean	SD
		1	2	3	4	5		
1	He sets the personal example of what he expected from others	1 (0.5)	4 (2.1)	23 (11.9)	103 (53.4)	62 (32.1)	4.15	0.743
	He spends time and energy on making certain that the people he works with adhere to the principles and standards that we have agreed on	0	3 (1.6)	25 (13)	110 (56.9)	55 (28.5)	4.12	0.681
3	He follows through on the promises and commitments that we make	1 (0.5)	0	27 (14)	107 (55.4)	58 (30.1)	4.15	0.684
4	He is clear about his philosophy of leadership	1 (0.5)	1 (0.5)	23 (12)	107 (55.4)	61 (31.6)	4.17	0.69
	He makes certain that we set achievable goals, make concrete plans and establish measurable milestones for the projects and programs that we work on	1 (0.5)	4 (2.1)	25 (13)	110 (56.9)	53 (27.5)	4.09	0.727
6	He makes progress towards goals one step at a time	1 (0.5)	1 (0.5)	31 (16.1)	116 (60.1)	44 (22.8)	4.04	0.676
Sub-total (Average)							4.12	0.700

Note: SD = Standard Deviation, f = Frequency, (number) = (%)

Score: 1=Not effective, 2= Rarely effective, 3=Fairly effective, 4=Effective, 5=Very effective

It was found that the highest score statement for ‘Enable Others to Act’ was “He is clear about his philosophy of leadership” whereby most findings agreed to “Effective” that contributed 55.4% with 107 respondents. Another 31.6% agreed to “Very Effective” with 61 respondents meanwhile 12% agreed to “Fairly Effective” with 23 respondents. However, for both scores “Not effective” and “Rarely Effective” it showed that only 1 respondent each which 0.5% to each contribution. Therefore, the mean score for the

above statement was 4.17 with a standard deviation of 0.690. The lowest for statement was “He makes progress toward goals one step at a time”, indicated 116 (60.1%) respondents agreed to “Effective”, 44 respondents (22.8%) agreed to “Very Effective” and 31 (16.1%) respondents responded to “Fairly Effective” and only 1 (0.5%) respondent agreed to “Rarely Effective” and “Not Effective” to each contributed result. As a result, the mean score for the above statement was 4.04 with a standard deviation of 0.676.

Research Question 5: The Stakeholders’ Perceptions on Effectiveness of Encourage the Heart Practiced on School Achievements by Principals of Secondary Schools, Malaysia.

The stakeholders’ perceptions on effectiveness of Encourages the Heart practiced by principals on school achievements in Malaysia is presented on Table 5 below.

Table 5: Effectiveness of Encourages the Heart on School Achievements as practiced by Principals of Secondary Schools, Malaysia: Stakeholders’ Perceptions (n=193)

No	Items	Score, Frequency & Percentage (%)					Mean	SD
		1	2	3	4	5		
1	He praises people for a job well done	1 (0.5)	3 (1.6)	25 (13)	93 (48.2)	71 (36.7)	4.19	0.757
2	He makes it a point to let people know about his confidence in our abilities	4 (2.1)	7 (3.6)	54 (28)	95 (49.2)	33 (17.1)	3.76	0.853
3	He makes sure that people are creatively rewarded for their contributions to the success of our projects	1 (0.5)	3 (1.6)	49 (25.4)	105 (54.4)	35 (18.1)	3.88	0.73
4	He publicly recognizes people who exemplify commitment to share values	2 (1)	0	29 (15)	105 (54.4)	57 (29.6)	4.11	0.727
5	He finds ways to celebrate accomplishments	2 (1)	5 (2.6)	50 (25.9)	88 (45.6)	48 (24.9)	3.91	0.836
6	He gives the members of the team lots of appreciation and support for their contributions	1 (0.5)	2 (1)	27 (14)	104 (53.9)	59 (30.6)	4.13	0.721
	Sub-total (Average)						4.00	0.771

Note: SD = Standard Deviation, *f* = Frequency, (number) = (%)

Score: 1=Not effective, 2=Rarely effective, 3=Fairly effective, 4=Effective, 5=Very effective

Table 5 demonstrated that the highest score statement for ‘Encourage the Heart’ was “He praises people for a job well done”, just below half 48.2% indicated “Effective” with 93 respondents agreed to the statement and 71 respondents responded to “Very Effective” with 36.7%. A minority of respondent 13% indicated “Fairly Effective” with 25 respondents agreed to it. But, 3 of the respondents 1.6% indicated “Rarely Effective” and 1 respondent responded 0.5% indicated “Not Effective”. As a result, the mean score for the above statement was 4.19 with a standard deviation of 0.757. In contrast, the lowest for the above mean was “He makes it a point to let people know about my confidence in their abilities”, the majority commented that it was “Effective” with 95 (49.2%), 54 (28%) respondents “Fairly Effective”, 33 respondents (17.1%) responded “Very Effective”, 7 (3.6%) respondents indicated “Rarely Effective” and only 4

respondents agreed to "Not Effective" with 2.1% of the contribution. Therefore, the mean score for the above statement was 3.76 with a standard deviation of 0.853.

In summary, the findings of the above study correspond with Duignan, (2007), Bush (2010), Brauckmann & Pashiardis (2011), Gurr, Drysdale, Ylimaki & Jacobson (2011), Muijs (2011). Ornstein and Lunenburg (2012) who stated that the main principles of excellent schools were embedded in the principals' exemplary leadership practices especially a clear mission or set of a goals, practice of cordial teamwork, staff has the opportunity to be challenge and creative, parents and community members should recognize and value the school contributions.

Therefore, the above results are useful to the Ministry of Education in order to plan ahead what kind of training that are suitable for our educational leaders in the future. In addition, it gives some indication for strategies to value the principles role in educational field.

6. Conclusion

It can be concluded that exemplary leadership in educational setting is very significant in bringing the school organization towards success. The success depends very much on the leadership style and role that the principal practices in his work environment. It should be connected directly to one's ability to bring the right balance to the application of personal capabilities and capacities to perform task with group, prevailing values and norms among the leaders' group. Education has proven to be the root cause in supporting the current economic development. It produces a number of educators, businessmen, researchers and intellectuals in many sectors and fields. In recent globalization era particularly, without the injection of ideas and strategic planning from the government, our nation will be far behind from becoming a developed country in the future. Thus, education can be seen as the biggest contributor to our nation's development in order to support the continuous growth of quality human capital in our country. The fact is Malaysian government recently in its transformation programme and strategic plans so called National Key Result Area (NKRA) focuses more on education and academic performance outcomes towards the realization of Vision 2020 and Malaysian Education Development Plan 2013-2025.

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